

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight A405

16 August 1995

PACE Flight

For more information contact:

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FLIGHT FOLDER

DATE: 16 / 8 / 95 TAKE OFF 1137 H (local time) FLIGHT NO. A405
LANDING 1604

PROJECT OFFICER :

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST: K DEWEY

FLIGHT LEADER: M. Rule

OBSERVER:

OTHERS: 2D. M. PICKERING

CCN: D. FINDLEY

OZONE: D. TIDDEMAN

NAVA.) { P. HEALEY (SF26)

{ J. REID

S. HUDSON (SF26)

CAPTAIN: H. BURGOTNE

CO-PILOT: H. HENDERSON

NAVIGATOR: E. HENTON

ENGINEER: J. LAW

LOADMASTER: K. QUICK

13606

TRIALS INSTRUCTION (s) :

OPERATING AREA:

PLYMOUTH

GENERAL SYNOPTIC SITUATION :

TIME: 00Z

From sajh@atlas.plym.ac.uk Wed May 22 15:36:13 1996
Return-Path: <sajh@atlas.plym.ac.uk>
Received: from atlas.plym.ac.uk by mail.nerc-swindon.ac.uk with SMTP (PP)
id <20773-0@mail.nerc-swindon.ac.uk>; Wed, 22 May 1996 15:36:10 +0100
Received: from triton.plymouth.ac.uk
by atlas.plymouth.ac.uk (8.6.10/NERC-1.2(Solaris 2.x) id PAA13398;
Wed, 22 May 1996 15:34:16 +0100
From: Samantha Lavender <sajh@atlas.plym.ac.uk>
Message-Id: <9605221532.ZM16996@atlas.plymouth.ac.uk>
Date: Wed, 22 May 1996 15:32:37 +0100
X-Mailer: Z-Mail (3.2.0 26oct94 MediaMail)
To: A.Kaye@scientific-services.nerc.ac.uk
Subject: Met Flight Data
Mime-Version: 1.0
Content-Type: text/plain; charset=us-ascii
Status: R

>From our conversation my present requirements are for 1 Hz data including:

Windspeed & direction
Altitude (pressure & radar height)
GPS data (lat & long)
Air Temperature (true non-deiced)
Dew Point Temperature (total water and general eastern)
Ozone mixing ratio
PCASP measurements (calculated and raw)
Uncorrected radiometric data

You can login to triton.plymouth.ac.uk (141.163.100.8) using
account: uni
password: University

I have created a directory called metdata.

Best Wishes,

Sam

--

Samantha Lavender
NERC Remote Sensing & GIS Unit Tel: (01752) 233910
c/o Computing Service Fax: (01752) 233922
University Of Plymouth E-mail: S.Lavender@ncs.nerc.a
Drake Circus WWW: http://www.ragu.plymouth.ac.uk/
Plymouth, Devon, PL4 8AA

INCLUDE:

1. An assessment of the flight.
2. Summary of the weather conditions.

A successful flight with all sections of the sortie brief completed. The NERC aircraft was still in area on arrival so started with FL100 level runs otherwise as sortie, with three sets of level runs at FL100 FL050 and 2000' and two complete profiles which were extended to FL120 to clear haze top at about FL100.

On leaving Plymouth area low level run from south to north coast for ozone measurements.

Bbl cab at FL160 to west of Ci edge. 7 min leg box
Wind cab accelerating up and down wind runs 150-200 KTIAS

Anticyclone over UK with slack NEly over SW England.
Haze layers up to about FL100. Small cu developing over land. Vol tops above haze layer in North.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: ~~A. J. Davery~~ & K. Davery

Project: PACE Date: 16/8/95
 Flight No: A405 Page 1 of 5

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
1035								T/O BD. 5/8 C ₁ SEVERAL HAZE LAYERS ONCLIMB	
1044			FL 100		250			LEVEL FL 100 TRANSIT TO PACE AREA.	
1058		T	100		230	50.63	-3.60	1/8 small cu to W C ₁ clearing to W	
								Thick haze layers near this level. large variations in P _{cast} & O ₃	
1110								check on ozone pump.	
1116		T	100		192	50.83	-3.64	2/8 small cu below Haze layer just below C ₁ clearing to SW	
								As other a/c in area starting with FL 100 run then profile AB	
113018		S R1.1	100		192	50.38	-4.25	START LEVEL RUN FL 100. THICK HAZE LAYER JUST BELOW CLEAR ABOVE.	
113249		E 1.1	100		183	50.1	-4.27	O ₃ ~ 69 ppb DP -16.3 NEP 0.04 PC ~ 70 Extend for 1 min	
113624		S 1.2	100		032	50.20	-4.29	Haze layers 1/8 small cu over land. C ₁ to E.	
113940		E 1.2	100		028	50.38	-4.15	extend for start of profile from L20	
114249		S 1.3	100		142	50.34	-4.15		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: PACE Date: 16/8/95

Aircraft Scientist: ~~A. Savage~~ & K. Dawcy.

Flight No: A405 Page 2 of 5

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
1143		E 1.3	100		145	50.30 -4.09	climb to FL120 for profile to clear haze layers		
114520		S P1	120		173	50.22 -4.09			
114816		HOLD P1	090						
114859		Restart P1	090		266	50.03 -4.13	HAZE layer ~ 9000' - to surface - thickest ~ 4000'		
1154			Passing 3000				increase in O ₃ slow turn.		
120002		E P1	50'		91	50.22 -4.35	increase in neph from 1158 to 1200 climb for next level 2000' starting point A		
120532		S R2.1	2000'		192	50.30 -4.25			
120750		E 2.1				50.19 -4.30	PC ~ 850 O ₃ ~ 85 neph ~ 0.1 → 0.45 SST 18.5		
121144		S 2.2	2000'		021	50.19 -4.30	small an overland clear over sea Haze 4/8 Ci to E.		
121540		E 2.2				50.38 -4.16	SST cal in turn.		
121808		S 2.3	2000'		136	50.37 -4.20			
121906		2.3				50.32 -4.11	climb for next level		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: RACE Date: 9/8/95

Aircraft Scientist: M. K. & K. Dewey

Flight No: A408 Page 3 of 5

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
122225		SE P2	FL 50			50.27 -4.21			
122609		S 3.1	FL 50		196	50.31 -4.42	in-thick haze layer 03 ~ 61 neph 04 PC ~ 500		
122842		E 3.1	FL 50			50.18 -4.27			
123257		S 3.2	FL 50			50.21 -4.30	Haze layer cu building overland.		
123654		E 3.2	FL 50			50.39 -4.16	1/8 Cu base 500'		
123942		S 3.3	FL 50		133	50.36 -4.19	DEF		
124033		E 3.3	FL 50		142	50.33 -4.14	end level r. was climb for last profile.		
124458		S P3	FL 120		276	50.26 -4.44	Haze top ~ 850'		
124826		HOLD P3	FL 80		←	50.23 -4.73			
124930		Restart P3	80		107	50.2 -4.69			
130015		E P3	50'			50.10 -3.91	Neph peak 107 ENH 1024 552. END OF RACE MEASUREMENTS. Position for coast in low level.		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye & K. Dancy*

Project: PACE

Date: *16/8/95*

Flight No: A405

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
130232		S R4	ASL 1000		343	50.23	-3.69	LOW LEVEL OZONE RUN 1/8 Small Cir MAX O ₃ in S ~ 90 DEGR -68 - 57 N LEAST. 1310	
132447		E R4			N	51.26	-3.83	V LIGHT	
132729		S RS.1	100'		267	51.31	-3.93	SPEED RUNS WIND 090/2 VIS 4 MILES. STARTING @ 150 KTS PATCHY FOG.	
133211		E RS.1	100'			51.33	-4.27		
133425		S S.2	100'		086	51.34	4.27	RUN 2 STARTING 150 - 200	
1338		E S.2	100			51.37	-3.94		
134123		S 6.1	FL 50		256	51.37	-4.07	4/8 Cir above poor low level vis 150-200	
134542		E 6.1	FL 50			51.29	-4.44		
134659		S 6.2	FL 50		075	51.34	-4.42	150-200	
13121		E 6.2	FL 50			51.	-4		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: KD

Project: PACE

Date: 6/8/95

Flight No: 405

Page 5 of 5

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
1358								over land 1/8 mainly small cu 1501 tops above haze layer to 120	
140505		S 7.1	FL 160		220	50.64 -4.65		SOLA 2 IS. 7 MIN RUNS INTO SUN	
141205		E 7.1	FL 160		↖	50.36 -5.15			
141323		S 7.2	FL 160		308	50.37 -5.28		ACROSS SUN	
142023		E 7.2	FL 160		↘	50.70 -5.88			
142126		S 7.3	FL 160		039	50.77 -5.84		DOWN SUN	
142826		E 7.3	FL 160		↘	51.13 -5.42			
142928		S 7.4	FL 160		133	51.13 -5.32		Cl edge to E parallel to track now close to track.	
143628		E 7.4	FL 160			50.80 -4.77		END TRANSIT FL 150 TO BD.	
15								LAND BD	

INCLUDE:

1. An assessment of the flight.
2. Summary of the weather conditions.

A successful flight with all sections of the sortie brief completed. The NERC aircraft was still in area on arrival. So started with FL100 level runs otherwise as sortie, with three sets of level runs at FL100 FL050 and 2000' and two complete profiles which were extended to FL120 to clear haze top at about FL100.

On leaving Plymouth area low level run from south to north coast for ozone measurements.

BBR cab at FL160 to west of CI edge. 7 min leg box wind cab accelerating up and down wind runs 150-200 KT/A

Anticyclone over UK with slack NEly over SW England. Haze layers up to about FL100. Small cu developing over land. Vol tops above haze layer in North.

103642

Take Off from Boscombe

PACE

113018(2) - 113239(3)	Run 1.1, A → B	FL100	200°
113626(4) - 113940(5)	Run 1.2, B → C	FL100	035°
114249(6) - 114341(7)	Run 1.3, D → F	FL100	150°
114520(8) - 120002(13)	PROFILE P1 ↓	FL120 → 50ft	turning
120532(15) - 120756(16)	Run 2.1, A → B	2000ft	200°
121144(17) - 121540(18)	Run 2.2 B → C	2000ft	035°
121808(19) - 121906(20)	Run 2.3, D → F	2500ft	150°
121906(20) - 122225(21)	PROFILE P2 ↗	2000ft → FL50	150/015°
122609(22) - 122842(23)	Run 3.1, A → B	FL50	030°
123257(24) - 123644(25)	Run 3.2, B → C	FL50	030°
123942(26) - 124033(28)	Run 3.3, D → F	FL50	150°
124458(29) - 130015(33)	PROFILE P3 ↓	FL120 → 50ft	turning
<u>low level ozone sampling</u> 1301 - 132447(30)	Run 4	400'agl	

Accelerating Runs

132729(37) - 133211(48)	Run 5.1	100ft	
133425(49) - 133840(60)	Run 5.2	100ft	
134123(61) - 134542(72)	Run 6.1	FL50	
134659(73) - 135121(84)	Run 6.2	FL50	
<u>Box Pattern</u> 140505(85) - 141205(86)	Run 7.1	FL160	225°
141323(87) - 142023(88)	Run 7.2	FL160	315°
142126(89) - 142826(90)	Run 7.3	FL160	050°
142928(91) - 143628(92)	Run 7.4	FL160	140°

150358

Land at Boscombe

MRF 01 — P.A.C.E. Experiment (SeaWiFs)

A405 16/8/95

Location: Plymouth area as show on map and in flightline table for main experiment

Meteorological Conditions: Clear skies with less than 2 octas cloud cover.

Flight Patterns:

1. Transit from Boscombe Down to operational area to arrive overhead at FL 100
2. Profile descent from FL 100 to minimum safe altitude (50 feet) along flight line C-B.
3. Straight and level runs along flight lines A-B, B-C and D-E-F starting at 2000ft then FL 050 and FL 100.
4. Profile descent from FL 100 to 50ft remaining within operating area.
- * 5. Vacate Plymouth area by 1400 BST and transit as convenient for next section to allow radiometers to stabilise temperatures.
6. Calibration box pattern FL 150 when radiometer temps are reported stable.

10 min run into sun

10 min run across sun

10 min run down sun

10 min run across sun. Box pattern can be started on any leg as convenient

7. Accelerating runs from 150 kts to 200 Kt, only if low turbulence.

Accelerating by 10 Kt at intervals of 30 seconds. Race track, one run with wind and one run into wind. Minimum height (100 ft) and 5,000 ft.

8. Items 6 and 7 can be transposed if convenient.

9. Return to Boscombe Down

Special Requirements: MRF radar operator to have control of radar as often as possible and note of radar elevation when Nav has control.

Communications: G-NERC a/c 130.625 MHz callsign Atlantic 31

K.J.Dewey a/s

* low level run to N Devon.

Run Positions

A. Rame Head	50° 18.60 N	04° 13.36 W
B. Eddystone	50° 10.80 N	04° 15.90 W
B. Eddystone	50° 10.80 N	04° 15.90 W
C. Mount Batten	50° 21.50 N	04° 07.81 W
D. Mount Edgcumbe	50° 21.48 N	04° 10.22 W
E. East Breakwater	50° 19.99 N	04° 08.12 W
F. Renny Point	50° 19.02 N	04° 07.34 W

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: ~~A. J. ...~~ & K. Davey.

Project: PACE Date: 16/8/95
 Flight No: A405 Page 1 of 5

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
1035								T/O BD. 5/8 CI SEVERAL HAZE LAYERS ONCLIMB	
1044			FL 100		250			LEVEL FL 100 TRANSIT TO PACE AREA.	
1058		T	100		230	50.63	-3.60	1/8 small cu to W CI clearing to W	
								Thick haze layers near this level. large variations in PCASP & O ₃	
1110								check on ozone pump.	
1116		T	100		192	50.83	-3.64	2/8 small cu below haze layer just below CI clearing to SW	
								As other a/c in area starting with FL 100 Ven then profile AB	
113018		S R1.1	100		192	50.38	-4.25	START LEVEL RUN FL 100. THICK HAZE LAYER JUST BELOW CLEAR ABOVE.	
113249		E 1.1	100		183	50.1	-4.27	O ₃ ~ 69 ppb DP -16.3 NEPH 0.04 PC ~ 70 Extend for 1 min	
113624		S 1.2	100		032	50.20	-4.29	Haze layers 1/8 small cu over land. CI to E.	
113940		E 1.2	100		028	50.38	-4.15	extend for start of profile from L20	
114249		S 1.3	100		142	50.34	-4.15		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: PAGE Date: 16/8/81

Aircraft Scientist: A. Page & K. Dawcy.

Flight No: A405 Page 2 of 5

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
1143		E 1.3	100		145	50.30 -4.09	climb to FL120 for profile to clear haze layers		
114520		S P1	120		173	50.22 -4.09			
114816		HOLD P1	90						
114859		RESUME P1	090		266	50.03 -4.13	HAZE layers ~ 9000' to surface - thickest ~ 4000'		
1154			PAUSE 3000				increase in O ₃ slow down.		
120002		E P1	50'		91	50.22 -4.35	increase in neph from 1158 to 1200 climb for next level 2000' starting point A		
120532		S R2.1	2000'		192	50.30 -4.25			
120750		E 2.1				50.19 -4.30	PC ~ 850 O ₃ ~ 85 neph ~ 0.1 → 0.45 SST 18.5		
121144		S 2.2	2000'		021	50.19 -4.30	small in overland clear over sea Haze 4/8Li to E.		
121540		E 2.2				50.38 -4.16	SST cal in turn		
121808		S 2.3	2000'		136	50.37 -4.20			
121906		2.3				50.32 -4.11	climb for next level		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: RACE Date: 9/6/81

Aircraft Scientist: *M. Kaye & K. Dewey*

Flight No: A405 Page 3 of 5

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
122225		<i>SE</i> <i>3/P2</i>	FL 50			50.27 -4.21			
122609		S 3.1	FL 50		196	50.31 -4.42	<i>in-thick haze layer 03-61 neph 04 PC ~ 500</i>		
122842		E 3.1	FL 50			50.18 -4.27			
123257		S 3.2	FL 50			50.21 -4.30	<i>Haze layer Cu building overland.</i>		
123654		E 3.2	FL 50			50.39 -4.16	<i>1/8 Cu base 5000'</i>		
123942		S 3.3	FL 50		133	50.36 -4.19		DEF	
124033		E 3.3	FL 50		142	50.33 -4.14	<i>end level r.c. as climb in last profile.</i>		
124458		S P3	FL 120		276	50.26 -4.44	<i>Haze top ~ 8500'</i>		
124826		HOLD P3	FL 80		←	50.23 -4.73			
124930		Restart P3	80		107	50.2 -4.69			
130015		E P3	50'			50.10 -3.91	<i>Neph peak ~ 7 SWH 1024 SS2.</i> <i>END OF RACE MEASUREMENTS.</i> <i>Position for coast in low level.</i>		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTISTS LOG

Project: YACE

Date: 10/8/75

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye & K. Dancy

Flight No: A405

Page 4 of

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
130232		S R4	ASL 1000		343	50.23	-3.69	LOW LEVEL OZONE RUN 1/8 Small Cu Max O ₃ in S ~ 90 DEGR -68 - 57 N LEAST 1310	
132447		E R4			N	51.26	-3.83	V LIGHT	
132729		S RS.1	100'		267	51.31	-3.93	<u>SPEED RUNS</u> . WIND 090/2 VIS 4 MILES. STARTING @ 150 KTS PATCHY FOG.	
133211		E RS.1	100'			51.33	-4.27		
133425		S S.2	100'		086	51.34	4.27	RUN 2 STARTING 150 - 200	
1338		E S.2	100			51.37	-3.94		
134123		S 6.1	FL 50		256	51.37	-4.07	4/8 Cu above poor low level vis 150-200	
134542		E 6.1	FL 50			51.29	-4.44		
134659		S 6.2	FL 50		075	51.34	-4.42	150-200	
13121		E 6.2	FL 50			51.	-4		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *KD*

Project: *PACE* Date: *16/8/95*
 Flight No: *405* Page *5* of *5*

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
1358								<i>over land.</i> <i>1/8 mainly small cu 1501 tops above haze layer to 120</i>	
140505		<i>S</i> <i>7.1</i>	<i>FL</i> <i>160</i>		<i>220</i>	<i>50.64</i> <i>-4.65</i>		<i>SOLAR 215.</i> <i>INTO SUN</i> <i>7 MIN RUNS</i>	
141205		<i>E</i> <i>7.1</i>	<i>FL</i> <i>160</i>		<i>↖</i>	<i>50.36</i> <i>-5.15</i>			
141323		<i>S</i> <i>7.2</i>	<i>FL</i> <i>160</i>		<i>308</i>	<i>50.37</i> <i>-5.28</i>		<i>ACROSS SUN</i>	
142023		<i>E</i> <i>7.2</i>	<i>FL</i> <i>160</i>		<i>↘</i>	<i>50.70</i> <i>-5.88</i>			
142126		<i>S</i> <i>7.3</i>	<i>FL</i> <i>160</i>		<i>039</i>	<i>50.77</i> <i>-5.84</i>		<i>DOWN SUN</i>	
142826		<i>E</i> <i>7.3</i>	<i>FL</i> <i>160</i>		<i>↘</i>	<i>51.13</i> <i>-5.42</i>			
142928		<i>S</i> <i>7.4</i>	<i>FL</i> <i>160</i>		<i>133</i>	<i>51.13</i> <i>-5.32</i>		<i>Cl edge to E parallel to track now close to track.</i>	
143628		<i>E</i> <i>7.4</i>	<i>FL</i> <i>160</i>			<i>50.80</i> <i>-4.77</i>		<i>END TRANSIT FL 150 TO BD.</i>	
15								<i>LAND B/D</i>	

NEPHELOMETER OPERATORS LOG

FLIGHT H405

DATE 16 108 195

PROJECT PAGE

PART 1 of 1

G.M.T.	HEIGHT	I.A.S.	RUN	Bscat	REMARKS
0845	GROUND CAL		—	3.3 / 3.4	
0855	GROUND RUN		—	0.3 / 0.4	
0955	"		—	0.5 / 0.6	
1000	GROUND CAL		—	3.6 / 3.8	
1014	GROUND RUN		—	0.6 / 0.7	
1048	AIR CAL	160	TRANSIT	3.0 3.0	
1044 30	RUN	180	"	0.1 / 0.2	
1106	10 000	180	TRANSIT	0.125	
1121	10 000	180	TRANSIT	0.37	
1131	10 000	180	RUN 1	0.12	
1137	"	"	RUN 1-2	0.06	
1144	10 000	"	1.3	0.1	
1145 20	12000 ↓	180	P1	0.02	
1207	2000	180	RUN 2.1	0.27	
1212	"	"	2.2	0.35	
1424	CAL ON	BOX 1 AT		16000 FT IAS = 180	3.4 / 3.5

DATE 16/8/97 TI MRF 01 A-2 NAV HEATON 1019
 AIRFIELD Blaown AIRFIELD Blaown 126 J'
 R/W 23 W/V 350/A TEMP +22 QNH 1024 OFF 2482. R/W 23 W/V 320/15 TEMP +22 QNH 1022 OFF 2410
 WX 7x3000 WX br m. B2. / L/A 31K
 ATC CL RT 260 St 4 ATC CL S- V 1200 1+5300 3+300

T/O TIME 1035 LAND TIME 1:27 1070. W/S

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG	RUN
113019	192				206	14/12	1200		N50187 W004134	ST 2-1
113238							✓	1013	N50108 W004160	EN 1-1
113626						L/U	✓		✓	ST 2-2
113926						L/U	✓		N50215 W004078	EN 1-2
114227						L/U	✓		N50215 W004102	1-3
114325						L/U	✓		N50193 W004067	EN 1-3
114720						08/15	1200		N50142 W004083	P1
114900						L/U	50		N50130 W004202	EPP 1
120524	190	X	X	X	190	✓	2000	1020	N50186 W004134	ST 2-1
120758							✓		N50108 W004169	EN 2-1
121144	027					070/5	2000	1020	---	ST 2-2
121539							2000	1020	N50215 W004078	EN 2-2
121809	146					✓	2000		N50215 W004110	ST 2-3
121906							2000		N50200 W004081	EN 2-3
✓							2000		✓	STAGE P2
12226							2000		N50150 W004122	EN P2
122609							1250		N50186 W004134	ST R3-1
122841					197	L/U	1250		N50108 W004159	EN R3-1
123256	026				198	L/U	1250		---	S 3-2
123645					202	083/7	1250		N50215 W004078	EN 3-2
123912						✓	1250		N50186 W004134	ST 3-3
124032							1250		N50190 W004073	EN 3
✓							1200		---	---

(121)

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT / LONG	RUI.
124457							R120	2942	NS0157 W004239	B
130017	061			180	180	136/7	50'	NAV AL	NS0045 W00352.5	END P3
130400	355					078/8	250 AL	NAV AL	NS0132 W003385	Rev 4
132414							✓		NS1117 W003298	Rev 4
122724	267			150 200		VAP SPEED	100		NS1147 W003470	ST Rev 5
122211							100' AL		NS1126 W00415.6	END 1.5
132222	085			170 250		VAP SPEED	100' AL	NAV	NS1205 W00417.2	ST Rev 5-2
133840							100		NS1221 W003570	END 6
134122				150 200			R250	FL	NS1221 W004037	ST R 1
134524	260					332/07	R50	2942	NS1178 W004250	END R 1
134700	080			150 200			R250		NS1201 W004265	ST R 2
135116							R250		NS12200 W004020	END 6-2
140505	220	-	-	180	202	119/12	R160	(R) 342	NS0415 W004384	ST 7-1
141205							✓		NS024 W005089	END 1
141223	310			180	✓	120/13	R160		NS0225 W005164	ST 7-2
141923							✓		NS0414 W005164	END 2
142125	041			✓		12-12	F160		NS0414 W00516	ST 7-3
142825							✓		NS1089 W005252	END 1-3
142828	13A					130/10	✓		NS1077 W005198	ST 7-4
143828									NS0480 W004466	END 7-4
								118		
								30	10A	888 18 1485
									Rev 1	3A 141502
								NAV 1		3 1505
224									(27) 28	

230
225/3.6/005/28
1160

1138
1506

A405

16-AUG-95

10:44:33

001 Ω

51.05

-2.30 AS P

HDG degT	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s	
259.	697.	10.0	216.	4.6	-21.2	035/ 5	

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC #/cc 505
 PCASP MEAN RAD um 0.2
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 12.49

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 0.0
 FSSP LMC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE um 0
 2D-C LMC g/m3 0.000e+000

95-08-16 11:00:00

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1 0.1 10
 1 0.1 10

A405

16-AUG-95

11:13:30

001 Ω

50.99

-3.68 AS P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
169.	699.	9.9	213.	4.6	-16.9	190/ 2

DEW C -16.93 OZMR ppb 80.40

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A405 16-AUG-95 11:40:33 005 - 50.43 -4.13 AS P

ASPT	ASPT	ASPT	ASPT	ASPT	DEW	WIND
deg	deg	deg	knots	C	C	deg m/s
331.	700.	9.9	218.	4.3	-15.1	114/2

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

PCASP CONC/cc

1000

0

PCASP CONC	#/cc	573
PCASP MEAN RAD	um	0.1
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	4.85

FSSP CONC	#/cc	0
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	3.2
FSSP LWC	gm/m3	0.00

2D-C CONC	#/l	0.0
2D-C MAX SIZE	um	0
2D-C LWC	g/m3	0.000e+000

95-08-16 11:51:13

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1
1

0.1
0.1

10
10

A405

16-AUG-95

12:01:48

013 Ω

50.26

-4.24 FR P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
44.	952.	1.7	186.	19.2	13.4	059/ 3

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT		FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A405

16-AUG-95

12:00:39

013

50.22

-4.30 AS P

HDC	REF	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg	ft	ft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
40.	1000.	0.4	177.	20.6	14.1	142 / 4

A	B	C	D		F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A405

16-AUG-95

12:01:48

013 Ω 50.26

-4.24 FR P

HDG degT 44.	SPR mb 952.	PHGT kft 1.7	TAS knots 186.	TAT C 19.2	DEW C 13.4	WIND deg m/s 059/3
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A SELECT	B	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
-------------	---	-----------	-----------	---	---	------------	-----------

A405

16-AUG-95

12:41:30

028

Ω

50.28

-4.10 RV P

HDG degT 182.	SPR mb 791.	PHGT kft 6.7	TAS knots 180.	TAT C 9.6	DEW C -0.3	WIND deg m/s 073/ 2
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OZMR
ppb

66.73

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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A405

16-AUG-95

12:42:42

028

50.26

-4.20 AS P

HDC	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg T	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
270.	733.	8.7	185.	4.9	-8.2	092/3

OZMR
ppb

61.20

S. TEMP
C

16.47

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM	—	—	VIDEO	HELP

A405 16-AUG-95 13:00:57 033 Ω 50.12 -3.86 AS

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
55.	1010.	0.1	195.	20.2	14.0	131 / 4

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

** TOTAL PAGE .001
MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_2 PAGE.001

16 AUG '95 3:45

WED 00Z

DT 00Z WED 16/ 8/95 VT 00Z WED 16/ 8/95 GMAIN T+ 0 --- THICKNESS DM. 500-1000MB
HEIGHT DM. 500MB

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_1 PAGE.001

16 AUG '95 6:32

DATA TIME: 160500 AUG 1995
SCALE 1: 2 500 000 UK
DATA CUTOFF TIME: 06:37

06 16/8

0705

10N

62105
15 18A
15
15
0805

15 209
15
15

15 227
15
15
8/06
8/03

14 234
02
14

16 233
84
16
17/18

13 236
65
12

17 234
80
19
7/35
1/15

14 243
80
11
60
4/15 14

13 235
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13
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15 239
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14

13 242
70
11

13 243
04
17/35

14 247

14 638
18
12

18 626
97
14

13 182
82
13

17 204
81
14

16
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MSBW4
15 220
88
14
7/3

17 223
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14
3/25
1/14

13 227
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11 235
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14 232
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15 239
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13 227
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14 232
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15 242
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08 249
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15 247
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63111
15 198
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0402

62112
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0403

62109
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0501

62159
18 228
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0301
0401

62122
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LFSU
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CAV
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DATA TIME: 160600 AUG 1995
 SCALE 1: 2 500 000 U1
 DATA CUTOFF TIME: 06. 37

LA 03 21

10	090	11
15	075	12
20	095	12
25	115	16
30	090	9
40	115	6
50	115	4
60	115	3
70	120	
85		
100	110	5

MAX NIL

TROP 187 -59

10	1659
15	1405
20	1224
25	1000
30	958
40	755
50	597
60	320
85	160
100	21

10	254.0
15	181.0
20	144.0
25	122.0
30	203.0
40	169.0
50	266.9
60	299.2
85	139.6
100	566.1

10	-60
15	-57
20	-57

HRST 10 22

10	090	15
15	065	16
20	090	16
25	085	12
30	085	26
40	050	16
50	030	15
60	040	9
70	020	8
85	345	15
100		

MAX NIL

TROP 187 -65

10	1658
15	1406
20	1224
25	1001
30	958
40	753
50	596
70	319
85	159
100	20

10	254.0
15	180.0
20	143.0
25	123.0
30	205.0
40	167.0
50	267.1
60	299.2
85	159.1
100	566.3

10	-60
15	-58
20	-60

LA 03 26

10	065	17
15	065	17
20	075	13
25	060	32
30	060	27
40	360	21
50	020	18
60	005	10
70	325	17
85	310	12
100		

MAX NIL

TROP 175 -64

10	1658
15	1404
20	1226
25	1002
30	959
40	754
50	595
70	319
85	158
100	20

10	254.0
15	178.0
20	144.0
25	123.0
30	205.0
40	169.0
50	266.5
60	298.7
85	138.4
100	565.2

10	-60
15	-59
20	-59

HRST 10 26

10	075	7
15	085	17
20	110	30
25	105	30
30	100	18
40	080	8
50	225	3
60	060	8
70		
85	325	9
100		

MAX NIL

TROP 174 -63

10	1661
15	1407
20	1229
25	1005
30	962
40	756
50	597
70	319
85	158
100	20

10	254.0
15	178.0
20	144.0
25	123.0
30	206.0
40	169.0
50	268.0
60	298.6
85	137.9
100	566.6

10	-60
15	-59
20	-59

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms:	Form Title
1	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet
5	Aircraft Scientist log
1	Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements
1	Interactive log
1	Flight Leader pre-flight check form
2	Flight Leader in-flight check form
4	Flight Leader in-flight log
2	Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
	MCR log
	CCN log
	MARSS log
	Chemistry log
1	<i>Nephelometer</i> Particulate/Filter boom Operator's log
3	2DK/FSSP/Holography Operator's log
	Sonde Ejector's log
1	Navigator's log
	Photographic log (photocopy original)
✓	Instrument status forms
✓	RTD prints
✓	Raw data plots
✓	Signal register
	Weather charts
	Satellite pictures
	Omega track
	Electronics pre-flight
	Mechanical fit

A405 16-AUG-95 11:30:18-13:00:15GMT

mercator_projection

INS TRACK - run no

A405 16-AUG-95 Height time series

PACE Profile 1

PACE Profile 2

| TTDI

| GEDP

: TWDP

TOTAL WATER

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P1

Times 11:45:20-12:00:02 GMT

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P1

Times 11:45:20-12:00:02 GMT

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P1

Times 11:45:20-12:00:02 GMT

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P3

TOTAL WATER

Times 12:44:58-13:00:15 GMT

1 second averages

GENERAL EASTERN

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P3

Times 12:44:58-13:00:15 GMT

seconds averages

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P3

Times 12:44:58-13:00:15 GMT

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P1

Times 11:45:20-12:00:02 GMT

Parameter no. 580

Parameter no. 581

Parameter no. 578

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P1

Times 11:45:20-12:00:02 GMT

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
Parameter no. 575

DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 520

DEW POINT (DEG K)
Parameter no. 521

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P1

Times 11:45:20-12:00:02 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P1

Times 11:45:20-12:00:02 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P1

Times 11:45:20-12:00:02 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P3

Times 12:44:58-13:00:15 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)
Parameter no. 580

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
Parameter no. 581

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
Parameter no. 578

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P3

Times 12:44:58-13:00:15 GMT

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P3

Times 12:44:58-13:00:15 GMT

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 515

AERO SCATT COEFF (10-4M-1)

Parameter no. 657

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P3

Times 12:44:58-13:00:15 GMT

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
Parameter no. 919

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)
Parameter no. 920

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)
Parameter no. 921

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95 Profile P3

Times 12:44:58-13:00:15 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.1

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 142
Mean 50.2451
Standard dev 4.068212e-02
Max value 50.3129
Min value 50.1743

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 142
Mean -4.25458
Standard dev 1.122440e-02
Max value -4.23302
Min value -4.26817

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 142
Mean 3029.19
Standard dev 3.99088
Max value 3035.97
Min value 3022.25

1 second averages

11:30:18 11:30:53 11:31:28 11:32:03 11:32:39
TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.1

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 142
Mean 0.155462
Standard dev 1.699378e-02
Max value 0.284930
Min value 0.131408

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 142
Mean 0.143582
Standard dev 9.921459e-03
Max value 0.185378
Min value 0.121281

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 142
Mean 0.183818
Standard dev 5.065444e-02
Max value 0.672829
Min value 0.152730

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

11:30:18 11:30:53 11:31:28 11:32:03 11:32:39

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.1

CORR UPPER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1019
No. of obs 142
Mean 890.008
Standard dev 1.37420
Max value 895.168
Min value 887.636

CORR LOWER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1022
No. of obs 142
Mean 71.9108
Standard dev 6.14281
Max value 94.3477
Min value 66.0410

CORR UPPER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1020
No. of obs 142
Mean 438.686
Standard dev 1.18591
Max value 442.609
Min value 436.800

11:30:18 11:30:53 11:31:28 11:32:03 11:32:59

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.1

CORR LOWER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1023
No. of obs 142
Mean 17.7188
Standard dev 4.57570
Max value 34.8655
Min value 13.7181

CORR UPPER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1021
No. of obs 142
Mean 206.005
Standard dev 0.648054
Max value 207.291
Min value 204.496

CORR LOWER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1024
No. of obs 142
Mean 364.342
Standard dev 1.38639
Max value 368.519
Min value 362.263

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.2

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 195
Mean 50.2789
Standard dev 4.984294e-02
Max value 50.3628
Min value 50.1911

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 195
Mean -4.18918
Standard dev 3.846464e-02
Max value -4.12487
Min value -4.25948

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 195
Mean 3029.72
Standard dev 4.88822
Max value 3036.70
Min value 3022.44

1 second overages

11:36:26 11:37:14 11:38:03 11:38:51 11:39:40
TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.2

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 195
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 195
Mean 277.676
Standard dev 0.104065
Max value 277.850
Min value 277.435

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 195
Mean 257.742
Standard dev 0.623980
Max value 259.033
Min value 256.479

11:36:26 11:37:14 11:38:03 11:38:51 11:39:40
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.2

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 195
Mean 255.451
Standard dev 0.710169
Max value 256.945
Min value 253.857

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 195
Mean 5.33057
Standard dev 0.154249
Max value 5.58562
Min value 4.88742

AERO SCATT COEFF (10-4M-1)

Parameter no. 657
No. of obs 195
Mean 0.278484
Standard dev 3.342552e-02
Max value 0.355003
Min value 0.201201

1 second overages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.2

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 195
Mean 172.238
Standard dev 40.6973
Max value 268.476
Min value 52.7266

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 195
Mean 0.135576
Standard dev 5.814554e-03
Max value 0.150734
Min value 0.109218

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 195
Mean 2.94197
Standard dev 1.18906
Max value 9.94547
Min value 0.607407

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.2

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 195
Mean 0.158282
Standard dev 1.252116e-02
Max value 0.224979
Min value 0.131583

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 195
Mean 0.146681
Standard dev 6.787568e-03
Max value 0.168364
Min value 0.120188

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 195
Mean 0.185384
Standard dev 3.565222e-02
Max value 0.415142
Min value 0.144692

1 second averages

11:36:26 11:37:14 11:38:03 11:38:51 11:39:40
TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.2

CORR UPPER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1019
No. of obs 195
Mean 889.373
Standard dev 13.3625
Max value 894.795
Min value 783.646

CORR LOWER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1022
No. of obs 195
Mean 81.9212
Standard dev 18.3683
Max value 125.798
Min value 65.1936

CORR UPPER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1020
No. of obs 195
Mean 445.818
Standard dev 1.16187
Max value 450.167
Min value 443.953

11:36:26 11:37:14 11:38:03 11:38:51 11:39:20
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.2

CORR LOWER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1023
No. of obs 195
Mean 26.4236
Standard dev 14.8616
Max value 62.8903
Min value 13.1294

CORR UPPER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1021
No. of obs 195
Mean 208.065
Standard dev 0.962569
Max value 210.199
Min value 205.443

CORR LOWER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1024
No. of obs 195
Mean 366.837
Standard dev 4.69475
Max value 381.696
Min value 362.482

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.3

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 53
Mean 50.3278
Standard dev 1.036431e-02
Max value 50.3464
Min value 50.3109

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 53
Mean -4.14253
Standard dev 1.530136e-02
Max value -4.11527
Min value -4.16613

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 53
Mean 3056.57
Standard dev 6.94280
Max value 3071.46
Min value 3048.34

11:42:49 11:43:02 11:43:15 11:43:28 11:43:41
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.3

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 53
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 53
Mean 277.676
Standard dev 5.118310e-02
Max value 277.755
Min value 277.577

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 53
Mean 256.588
Standard dev 0.491820
Max value 257.135
Min value 255.518

11:42:49 11:43:02 11:43:15 11:43:28 11:43:41

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R1.3

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 53
Mean 253.621
Standard dev 0.389735
Max value 254.509
Min value 252.752

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 53
Mean 5.26682
Standard dev 6.639215e-02
Max value 5.39943
Min value 5.12015

AERO SCATT COEFF (10-4M-1)

Parameter no. 657
No. of obs 53
Mean 0.274762
Standard dev 3.240166e-02
Max value 0.345237
Min value 0.230497

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.1

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 145
Mean 285.020
Standard dev 1.07640
Max value 286.335
Min value 282.826

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 145
Mean 5.94259
Standard dev 0.231799
Max value 6.30710
Min value 5.46925

AERO SCATT COEFF (10-4M-1)

Parameter no. 657
No. of obs 145
Mean 0.434853
Standard dev 9.866469e-02
Max value 0.611333
Min value 0.223168

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.1

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 145
Mean 1262.84
Standard dev 345.532
Max value 2207.15
Min value 754.503

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 145
Mean $9.308641e-02$
Standard dev $2.522850e-03$
Max value $9.925622e-02$
Min value $8.806884e-02$

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 145
Mean 9.15907
Standard dev 4.59784
Max value 28.2679
Min value 4.34919

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.1

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 145
Mean 0.118299
Standard dev 1.502459e-02
Max value 0.173303
Min value 0.102161

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 145
Mean 0.102085
Standard dev 4.030440e-03
Max value 0.117189
Min value 9.506121e-02

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 145
Mean 0.163144
Standard dev 5.736926e-02
Max value 0.387395
Min value 0.116894

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.1

CORR UPPER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1019
No. of obs 145
Mean 799.555
Standard dev 3.13404
Max value 805.997
Min value 794.168

CORR LOWER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1022
No. of obs 145
Mean 42.7901
Standard dev 2.65686
Max value 55.0284
Min value 38.7778

CORR UPPER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1020
No. of obs 145
Mean 374.401
Standard dev 1.17043
Max value 377.516
Min value 371.844

12:05:32 12:06:08 12:06:44 12:07:20 12:07:56
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.1

CORR LOWER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1023
No. of obs 145
Mean 11.7955
Standard dev 1.98712
Max value 22.8948
Min value 9.41843

CORR UPPER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1021
No. of obs 145
Mean 330.239
Standard dev 0.948221
Max value 333.766
Min value 328.365

CORR LOWER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1024
No. of obs 145
Mean 414.018
Standard dev 0.809987
Max value 416.942
Min value 412.022

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.2

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 237
Mean 50.2690
Standard dev 5.258557e-02
Max value 50.3596
Min value 50.1801

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 237
Mean -4.19485
Standard dev 3.889604e-02
Max value -4.12936
Min value -4.26356

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 237
Mean 513.440
Standard dev 8.48597
Max value 535.891
Min value 496.521

12:11:44 12:12:43 12:13:42 12:14:41 12:15:40
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.2

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 237
Mean 626.400
Standard dev 9.33130
Max value 651.315
Min value 607.280

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 237
Mean 292.620
Standard dev 0.212501
Max value 293.163
Min value 292.235

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 237
Mean 286.266
Standard dev 0.866978
Max value 286.974
Min value 283.435

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.2

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 237
Mean 286.030
Standard dev 0.830237
Max value 286.724
Min value 283.434

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 237
Mean 5.84025
Standard dev 0.271739
Max value 6.44674
Min value 5.37616

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

AERO SCATT COEFF (10-4M-1)

Parameter no. 657
No. of obs 237
Mean 0.463187
Standard dev 6.221760e-02
Max value 0.618657
Min value 0.330585

AERO SCATT COEFF (10-4M-1)

12:11:44 12:12:43 12:13:42 12:14:41 12:15:40
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.2

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 237
Mean 1362.82
Standard dev 286.801
Max value 2067.69
Min value 571.797

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 237
Mean $9.117957e-02$
Standard dev $2.023496e-03$
Max value $9.821540e-02$
Min value $8.671895e-02$

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 237
Mean 8.61202
Standard dev 3.65378
Max value 26.6474
Min value 3.03912

1 second averages

12:11:44 12:12:43 12:13:42 12:14:41 12:15:40
TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.2

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 237
Mean 0.113628
Standard dev 1.306338e-02
Max value 0.182400
Min value 0.100510

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 237
Mean 9.950286e-02
Standard dev 3.582523e-03
Max value 0.118603
Min value 9.375483e-02

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 237
Mean 0.151289
Standard dev 4.840545e-02
Max value 0.431205
Min value 0.115459

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.2

CORR UPPER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1019
No. of obs 237
Mean 751.205
Standard dev 181.382
Max value 807.510
Min value 0.000000

CORR LOWER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1022
No. of obs 237
Mean 40.9945
Standard dev 5.67566
Max value 75.1067
Min value 35.3088

CORR UPPER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1020
No. of obs 237
Mean 374.034
Standard dev 46.0222
Max value 389.818
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.2

CORR LOWER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1023
No. of obs 237
Mean 11.8033
Standard dev 4.00242
Max value 36.5997
Min value 8.44615

CORR UPPER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1021
No. of obs 237
Mean 331.346
Standard dev 1.62732
Max value 336.275
Min value 328.380

CORR LOWER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1024
No. of obs 237
Mean 413.174
Standard dev 2.14216
Max value 427.247
Min value 410.945

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.3

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 55
Mean 50.3404
Standard dev 1.044649e-02
Max value 50.3573
Min value 50.3221

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 55
Mean -4.14955
Standard dev 1.491871e-02
Max value -4.12516
Min value -4.17508

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 55
Mean 518.352
Standard dev 4.69245
Max value 528.403
Min value 512.378

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.3

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 55
Mean 630.650
Standard dev 5.62065
Max value 640.539
Min value 615.455

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 55
Mean 293.028
Standard dev 0.213714
Max value 293.467
Min value 292.583

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 55
Mean 286.070
Standard dev 0.459435
Max value 286.838
Min value 285.469

12:18:08 12:18:21 12:18:35 12:18:48 12:19:02
TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.3

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 55
Mean 285.906
Standard dev 0.506725
Max value 286.731
Min value 285.216

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 55
Mean 6.01554
Standard dev 0.315278
Max value 6.49328
Min value 5.49253

AERO SCATT COEFF (10-4M-1)

Parameter no. 657
No. of obs 55
Mean 0.338974
Standard dev 4.310584e-02
Max value 0.420913
Min value 0.240257

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.3

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 55
Mean 1245.42
Standard dev 218.317
Max value 1813.78
Min value 898.883

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 55
Mean $9.174769e-02$
Standard dev $1.932569e-03$
Max value $9.554505e-02$
Min value $8.795798e-02$

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 55
Mean 7.91857
Standard dev 3.37632
Max value 19.1186
Min value 4.57053

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.3

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 55
Mean 0.113540
Standard dev 1.221574e-02
Max value 0.143785
Min value 0.101001

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 55
Mean 9.987462e-02
Standard dev 3.191831e-03
Max value 0.107957
Min value 9.441620e-02

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 55
Mean 0.149611
Standard dev 4.456176e-02
Max value 0.279403
Min value 0.115526

1 second averages

12:18:08 12:18:21 12:18:35 12:18:48 12:19:02
TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.3

CORR UPPER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1019
No. of obs 55
Mean 793.042
Standard dev 5.20699
Max value 801.301
Min value 780.165

CORR LOWER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1022
No. of obs 55
Mean 57.8466
Standard dev 10.5104
Max value 78.8159
Min value 46.5981

CORR UPPER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1020
No. of obs 55
Mean 369.643
Standard dev 11.5402
Max value 380.825
Min value 325.105

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R2.3

CORR LOWER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1023
No. of obs 55
Mean 25.3976
Standard dev 11.1089
Max value 47.7486
Min value 14.3017

CORR UPPER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1021
No. of obs 55
Mean 332.768
Standard dev 0.798832
Max value 335.393
Min value 330.630

CORR LOWER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1024
No. of obs 55
Mean 418.911
Standard dev 5.70302
Max value 432.849
Min value 414.383

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R3.1

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 154
Mean 50.2438
Standard dev 4.087887e-02
Max value 50.3140
Min value 50.1740

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 154
Mean -4.25390
Standard dev 1.117533e-02
Max value -4.23018
Min value -4.26761

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 154
Mean 1530.62
Standard dev 12.3144
Max value 1544.77
Min value 1504.93

12:26:09 12:26:47 12:27:25 12:28:03 12:28:42
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R3.1

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 154
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 154
Mean 286.601
Standard dev 0.105067
Max value 286.814
Min value 286.438

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 154
Mean 276.199
Standard dev 0.221052
Max value 276.614
Min value 275.669

12:26:09 12:26:47 12:27:25 12:28:03 12:28:42
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R3.1

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 154
Mean 276.247
Standard dev 0.259334
Max value 276.682
Min value 275.688

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 154
Mean 4.34777
Standard dev 4.369970e-02
Max value 4.44951
Min value 4.23197

AERO SCATT COEFF (10-4M-1)

Parameter no. 657
No. of obs 154
Mean 0.289354
Standard dev 3.089097e-02
Max value 0.357441
Min value 0.147490

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R3.1

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 154
Mean 514.091
Standard dev 50.6504
Max value 635.017
Min value 314.278

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 154
Mean 0.106276
Standard dev 1.850702e-03
Max value 0.111481
Min value 0.101753

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 154
Mean 4.06920
Standard dev 1.53125
Max value 13.8098
Min value 2.01584

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R3.1

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 154
Mean 0.122476
Standard dev 1.113019e-02
Max value 0.193024
Min value 0.113561

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 154
Mean 0.113327
Standard dev 3.321195e-03
Max value 0.127342
Min value 0.107676

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 154
Mean 0.144818
Standard dev 3.929268e-02
Max value 0.443294
Min value 0.125812

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R3.1

CORR UPPER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1019
No. of obs 154
Mean 852.218
Standard dev 2.74772
Max value 855.644
Min value 836.275

CORR LOWER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1022
No. of obs 154
Mean 61.1151
Standard dev 5.28329
Max value 85.3880
Min value 56.3154

CORR UPPER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1020
No. of obs 154
Mean 406.060
Standard dev 1.93107
Max value 409.778
Min value 397.338

1 second averages

12:26:09 12:26:47 12:27:25 12:28:03 12:28:42
TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R3.1

CORR LOWER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1023
No. of obs 154
Mean 15.9027
Standard dev 4.19340
Max value 35.5760
Min value 12.9964

CORR UPPER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1021
No. of obs 154
Mean 271.261
Standard dev 1.50057
Max value 275.135
Min value 268.856

CORR LOWER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1024
No. of obs 154
Mean 391.791
Standard dev 0.986341
Max value 396.170
Min value 390.109

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R3.2

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 228
Mean 50.2746
Standard dev 5.241588e-02
Max value 50.3629
Min value 50.1829

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 228
Mean -4.19607
Standard dev 4.145050e-02
Max value -4.12254
Min value -4.26680

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 228
Mean 1531.99
Standard dev 6.36973
Max value 1545.56
Min value 1515.91

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R3.2

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 228
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 228
Mean 286.565
Standard dev 7.726625e-02
Max value 286.813
Min value 286.355

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 228
Mean 276.469
Standard dev 0.271499
Max value 277.006
Min value 275.806

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R3.2

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 228
Mean 276.490
Standard dev 0.235076
Max value 277.007
Min value 275.728

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 228
Mean 4.30027
Standard dev 5.622723e-02
Max value 4.43074
Min value 4.17689

AERO SCATT COEFF (10-4M-1)

Parameter no. 657
No. of obs 228
Mean 0.269394
Standard dev 2.462385e-02
Max value 0.337911
Min value 0.198757

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R3.2

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 228
Mean 546.038
Standard dev 57.8792
Max value 683.485
Min value 384.713

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 228
Mean 0.105238
Standard dev 1.707863e-03
Max value 0.109842
Min value 0.100469

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 228
Mean 4.19882
Standard dev 1.69454
Max value 14.9431
Min value 2.53694

1 second averages

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R3.2

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 228
Mean 0.121296
Standard dev 1.155356e-02
Max value 0.186559
Min value 0.112046

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 228
Mean 0.112198
Standard dev 3.179154e-03
Max value 0.126228
Min value 0.106187

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 228
Mean 0.143803
Standard dev 4.214247e-02
Max value 0.408962
Min value 0.124091

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A405 16-AUG-95

Run no. R3.2

CORR UPPER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1019
No. of obs 228
Mean 847.990
Standard dev 1.41726
Max value 850.769
Min value 844.275

CORR LOWER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1022
No. of obs 228
Mean 65.4459
Standard dev 15.0080
Max value 117.001
Min value 52.8073

CORR UPPER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1020
No. of obs 228
Mean 412.882
Standard dev 22.6873
Max value 422.861
Min value 317.344

1 second averages

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Run no. R3.2

CORR LOWER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1023
No. of obs 228
Mean 20.0336
Standard dev 11.9121
Max value 59.6376
Min value 11.1806

CORR UPPER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1021
No. of obs 228
Mean 276.127
Standard dev 0.717827
Max value 277.942
Min value 274.260

CORR LOWER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1024
No. of obs 228
Mean 394.232
Standard dev 3.90245
Max value 412.212
Min value 391.509

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Run no. R3.3

GPS LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 580
No. of obs 52
Mean 50.3291
Standard dev 1.043552e-02
Max value 50.3466
Min value 50.3108

GPS LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 581
No. of obs 52
Mean -4.14194
Standard dev 1.376932e-02
Max value -4.11948
Min value -4.16492

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 52
Mean 1538.45
Standard dev 15.0262
Max value 1558.48
Min value 1516.77

1 second averages

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Run no. R3.3

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 52
Mean 1521.61
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1521.61
Min value 1521.61

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 52
Mean 286.433
Standard dev 9.935673e-02
Max value 286.585
Min value 286.245

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 52
Mean 276.695
Standard dev 0.105564
Max value 276.910
Min value 276.478

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

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Run no. R3.3

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 52
Mean 276.687
Standard dev 9.847645e-02
Max value 276.850
Min value 276.491

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 52
Mean 4.25310
Standard dev 4.331167e-02
Max value 4.35234
Min value 4.14509

AERO SCATT COEFF (10-4M-1)

Parameter no. 657
No. of obs 52
Mean 0.247536
Standard dev 4.083194e-02
Max value 0.325704
Min value 0.154814

1 second averages

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Run no. R3.3

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 52
Mean 562.188
Standard dev 58.9927
Max value 673.169
Min value 388.291

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 52
Mean 0.104210
Standard dev 1.393673e-03
Max value 0.107543
Min value 0.101145

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 52
Mean 4.19501
Standard dev 1.83684
Max value 14.7183
Min value 2.36946

1 second averages

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PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 52
Mean 0.119869
Standard dev 1.123662e-02
Max value 0.179180
Min value 0.111438

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 52
Mean 0.110905
Standard dev 2.838011e-03
Max value 0.122244
Min value 0.106278

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 52
Mean 0.142048
Standard dev 4.197121e-02
Max value 0.384777
Min value 0.122465

1 second averages

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Run no. R3.3

CORR UPPER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1019
No. of obs 52
Mean 851.011
Standard dev 3.47607
Max value 856.444
Min value 842.866

CORR LOWER CLR FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1022
No. of obs 52
Mean 85.0201
Standard dev 4.42069
Max value 94.7419
Min value 78.4918

CORR UPPER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1020
No. of obs 52
Mean 406.547
Standard dev 12.4150
Max value 416.237
Min value 341.144

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

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Run no. R3.3

CORR LOWER RED FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1023
No. of obs 52
Mean 34.3936
Standard dev 3.89426
Max value 43.3744
Min value 29.0802

CORR UPPER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1021
No. of obs 52
Mean 276.387
Standard dev 1.32608
Max value 279.154
Min value 274.410

CORR LOWER I/R FLUX (W M-2)

Parameter no. 1024
No. of obs 52
Mean 396.470
Standard dev 1.59242
Max value 400.527
Min value 393.705

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)